

Accessible Learning Labs

Artifact Description

To address the lack of effective accessibility education materials, we have created a comprehensive collection of labs to benefit accessibility education. These labs are collectively referred to as the *Accessible Learning Labs (ALL)*. The primary objectives of the labs is to educate participants on how to properly create accessible software, as well as to illustrate the need to create accessible software. Our interactive labs afford practitioners, instructors, and students the ability to engage with the material using only a browser.

We have also created a lab to address the problem of inequitable software. This easily adoptable, self-contained experiential activity is systematically designed to promote student interest in software ethics, with an emphasis on AI/ML bias. The activity involves participants selecting fabricated teammates based solely on their appearance. The participant then experiences either bias against themselves or bias against a teammate by the activity's fictitious AI.

How to Obtain the Artifact

Due to the labs' hosted nature, users require only a computer connected to the internet and a web browser (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, etc). The completed lab materials, which include lecture slides, videos, quizzes, and interactive activities, are available on our project website located at: <https://all.rit.edu>.

Replicating Paper Results

To replicate the results presented in the original paper, users may access the three variations of the activity at:

1. <https://all.rit.edu/Imagine1>
2. <https://all.rit.edu/Imagine2>
3. <https://all.rit.edu/Imagine3>